

ECONOMIC SCIENCES

E-COMMERCE IN KAZAKHSTAN: CHALLENGES AND PROBLEMS OF E-COMMERCE IN DEVELOPING COUNTRIES

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Abstract

The popularity of e-commerce is growing rapidly under the influence of various factors, and it is impossible to imagine the modern world without online stores, mobile applications that help you make purchases quickly at all levels. The article examines foreign experience in the development of electronic commerce and considers the problems and prospects for the development of the Kazakh e-commerce market.

Keywords: e-commerce, online commerce, online trades, Kazakhstani economy, developing countries, economic development.

Today, in developed and developing countries, electronic commerce is rapidly developing, its positive impact extends not only to the business sector, but also to the quality of life of the population as a whole. Namely, thanks to the development of electronic commerce, the population gets access to more goods at lower prices; the ability to compare prices for the necessary goods in different stores; the opportunity to purchase goods in the online stores of foreign suppliers directly through involvement in international trade. If you look at it from the point of view of the impact on business, it is worth noting that the growing popularity of e-commerce leads to an increase in the number of customers who want to open their own business in this area (Terezi, 2016).

In 2020, Kazakhstan has become one of the world leaders in the dynamics of e-commerce development. The rapid growth of the Kazakhstani domestic online market was largely due to tough government measures to limit the spread of infection. The digitalization of the economy of Kazakhstan, the use of modern methods of trade allows enterprises producing both consumer goods and goods for business to use all the possibilities of developing the local market and entering cross-border markets. E-commerce should become one of the drivers for the development of the Kazakhstani economy.

Currently, e-commerce still accounts for a small part of the world trade turnover (10-20%), but this is one of the most dynamically developing segments of trade and the economy of any country, characterizing the impact of digital changes in modern life.

At the beginning of 2021, out of 7.83 billion of the world's population, 59.5% use the Internet, 66.6% use mobile communications, and about 53.6% use social networks, while the majority use e-commerce platforms. The widespread use of electronic commerce is facilitated by the development of new technologies that ensure the simplicity and ease of any purchases on the Web, the constant growth in the number of online shopping sites available at any time of the day, the provision of complete information about the product and the increase in the level of protection of the buyer's rights. B2C trade (from business to consumer) without intermediaries in the form of distribution networks provides

lower prices for goods and saves time and money for buyers. The rapid growth of online shopping has led to a structural change in world trade, a change in the ratio of online and traditional (offline) trade (Pankomera & Greunen, 2019).

Manufacturers sell products directly to customers, bypassing a long chain of distributors, wholesalers and retailers. The study of the phenomenon of electronic commerce, as well as the collection, analysis and publication of statistical and analytical data in the form of reports, reports and reviews, are carried out by international organizations that regulate international trade (WTO, WCO, UNCTAD); international and national banks that record transfers of funds for online purchases through electronic payments; Associations that bring together participants in e-commerce; market research consulting companies; as well as the largest companies in the world (Mbayo Kabango & Romeo Asa, 2015). A number of countries publish official statistics on e-retail sales (US Bureau of the Census, National Bureau of Statistics of China, etc.).

In Kazakhstan, the public source of such information is the Association of Internet Trade Companies (AKIT), which accumulates data from various sources (Sberbank, OFD2), and the consulting firm Datalnsight3, which conducts its own surveys of key market participants. For countries where such data is not published, estimates of e-commerce volumes are provided from private sector market survey sources such as Statista4 surveys, IBM surveys5, Global-WebIndex6, Contentsquare7, SearchNode8 and others, as well as statistics from some of the largest companies operating in these markets. In this paper, we used the annual reports of these organizations for 2019-2021, which analyze e-commerce and the impact of the COVID-19 pandemic on its development.

E-commerce has been actively developing since its inception. Statistics include products and services ordered online through any device, regardless of the method of payment and does not include travel and tickets to various events, does not include payments, taxes and money transfers, ordering food and drinks on the spot, games, and purchases (alcohol, tobacco). This method of counting is used by all companies operating in this business (Alyoubi, 2015).

A review of the economic literature on the problems of the development of electronic commerce led to the conclusion that the concepts of "electronic business", "electronic commerce" and "electronic commerce" are actually recognized as synonyms. The terms "electronic commerce" and "electronic business" were first used at the end of the 20th century. leading corporations for the production of computer equipment and their software. They considered these concepts as the rationalization of production and economic activities with the help of digital technologies.

E-commerce is more than just buying and selling goods over the Internet. It covers the entire online pro-

cess of developing, marketing, selling, delivering, servicing, and paying for goods and services purchased in Internet-based, global customer markets supported by the worldwide web. Of course, there are also negative aspects of e-commerce, both for companies and for consumers. If for business it is the difficulty of conducting and legitimizing the activities of an enterprise on the Internet, then for consumers it is: consumer distrust in goods and services provided via the Internet; the inability to "touch" the product with your hands; an attractive platform for financial fraud; waiting for the delivery of the purchased goods. In general, these problems are quite solvable and eliminated (Kshetri, 2018).

Table 1.

Benefits of e-commerce

For business environment	For the consumer
Large sales volumes	The ability to view a wide range of goods and services without leaving home 24/7
Increasing the scope of the market for a product or service	Ubiquity
Cost reduction	Anonymity
Personalization	Prompt delivery
Fast time to market	cheaper goods and services
Frequent updates of product promotion software tools	Raising the standard of living

Geographically, e-commerce is growing most rapidly in the most technologically advanced countries, such as Europe, North America, Japan and China. This is due to the fact that in these countries the number of Internet users is increasing at an accelerated pace. So, in China, the USA, Great Britain every second inhabitant uses the Internet. In addition, the number of mobile users is growing. In particular, in China and the United States, the number of online buyers has already exceeded the number of offline buyers. The average world growth rate of the e-commerce market, according to the economic research agency eMarketer, fluctuates in the range of 18-20%. This is about 3-4% of the total retail volume in the Republic of Kazakhstan and 10-12% in the US and other highly developed countries. The average level of the e-commerce market on a global scale is about 6% (Alyoubi, 2015).

According to world experts, the fall of the e-commerce market abroad is not expected, since most of the largest market players in developed countries rely on e-commerce. Today, all companies have a developed plan for going online sales. Over time, more and more Western companies will open representative offices, warehouses, delivery systems to developing countries, as such companies as eBay, PayPal and others have already done (Kshetri, 2018).

In Kazakhstan, this type of entrepreneurial activity began to gain momentum during the period of accession to the World Trade Organization and the share of online commerce in total retail is about 1-1.5%, but the e-commerce market is growing by 30% annually. According to Satu.kz, the leader of online trade in Kazakhstan, in 2017, people in Kazakhstan bought goods for 20.144 billion tenge on the marketplace, and the average check for one online purchase increased by 19% and amounted to 34,742 tenge.

According to experts, the size of the e-commerce market in 2016 in Kazakhstan amounted to 226.4 billion tenge (about 660 million US dollars). The year-on-year growth was 45.4%. The e-commerce market share of retail turnover is 10%, in the future it is expected to grow to 15-18%, and after a few more years - up to 30%. The Southern capital accounts for almost 72% of the total market. To the Karaganda region - almost 12%, to Astana - 7.5% (Kuzhukeyeva, 2015).

If you pay attention to the preferences of Kazakhstani online buyers, clothes, shoes and accessories (56.8%) are usually in the lead here, food products are in second place (20.8%), and medicines are in third place (12%). Most online purchases are characterized by an average check in the range from 5 to 25 thousand tenge. The share of average checks up to 5 thousand tenge is 18.3%. From 25 to 50 thousand tenge - 19.2%, and over 50 thousand - 12.1%. It is logical that these figures also vary greatly depending on the region.

In order to accelerate the pace of development of the economy of the Republic of Kazakhstan and improve the quality of life of the population through the use of digital technologies in the medium term, as well as create conditions for the transition of the economy of Kazakhstan to a fundamentally new development trajectory that ensures the creation of the digital economy of the future in the long term, the government of the state adopted a digitalization program of Kazakhstan. It defines target indicators: the share of e-commerce in the total market of goods and services in 2017 - 7%, in 2020 - 10%; the share of turnover of Kazakhstani online stores in the total turnover of goods and services paid electronically in 2017 - 30%, in 2020 - 40% (Kuzhukeyeva, 2015).

To stimulate the development of electronic commerce, within the framework of the state program "Digital Kazakhstan", from January 1, 2018, tax legislation provides for tax incentives for persons engaged in electronic commerce in goods in the form of a full exemption from income tax until 2023. The right to a tax exemption is granted if the income from the activities of electronic trading in goods is at least 90% of the annual income.

Real results have also been achieved in the telecommunications sector. In Kazakhstan, preparations have begun for the implementation of the project "With optics - to the village." Within four years Kazakh-telecom JSC intends to lay optical communication lines in all villages where more than 250 people live. This project is of great importance for Kazakhstan. It will reduce the digital divide between rural and urban areas.

Thus, the main factors positively influencing e-commerce in Kazakhstan are:

- growth in the number of Internet users: The Internet is becoming faster and more accessible, as a result of which the Internet audience of Kaznet is growing;
- growth in the number and diversity of online stores: online commerce is looking for new forms, new products, new geography of influence;
- growth in the number of payment cards;
- improvement of the legal environment for online commerce (an example of this is the Law on Electronic Money adopted in Kazakhstan);
- creation of various institutions that help the development of the IT sector in the country.

At the same time, there are factors still constraining the growth of e-commerce in Kazakhstan, including:

- mistrust of users to this type of commercial transactions;
- lack of awareness and unwillingness of the population to use it;
- geographical restrictions of online stores existing in Kazakhstan (most of them work only in Almaty and Astana).

Therefore, the growth rate of e-commerce in Kazakhstan is still insignificant for the economy, the search for the most promising directions for the development and diversification of the e-commerce market

in Kazakhstan for the next 7-10 years, the possibility of its adaptation to the realities of the Kazakhstani consumer market is an urgent problem, the solution of which provides both enterprises and citizens, a number of benefits. For buyers, it means convenience, reliability, practicality, saving time when shopping. For sellers, it means an increase in markets of presence, growth in sales volumes, an increase in the turnover rate of working capital, and a reduction in costs, which together increase the competitiveness and stability of a business in a dynamic business environment.

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